

Wind or Current: Determining the key driver in seagrass floating fruit dispersal to optimize seed collection for aquaculture/restoration purposes

Version 1

Description

This project aims to experimentally quantify the movement ecology of *Posidonia oceanica* fruits under controlled conditions, using a current flume to simulate realistic combinations of currents and wind observed at sea. We aim to measure fruit speeds under 10 current and 8 wind intensities and 2 wind directions to provide useful data to model dispersal distances and trajectories of fruits at sea. In addition, improved identification of beachcast sites could facilitate seed collection efforts, making seed-based restoration techniques more practical and scalable. This approach would support the production of seedlings for transplantation, facilitating both aquaculture applications and large-scale *Posidonia oceanica* restoration initiatives.

All raw and processed data generated during this project, along with descriptive metadata and relevant scripts, will be deposited in the open-access repository Zenodo. The data will be made publicly available under a CC-BY 4.0 license after publication of the associated peer-reviewed article. An embargo may apply until formal publication to ensure proper referencing and citation

Funder

AQUASERV

Grant

AQUASERV – RESEARCH
INFRASTRUCTURE SERVICES

FOR SUSTAINABLE
AQUACULTURE, FISHERIES AND
THE BLUE ECONOMY
(corda_____he::101131121)

Researchers

Eduardo Infantes (0000-0002-9724-9237), Arturo Zenone (0000-0001-5540-7148), Trace Laskey (0009-0001-4299-4846), FABIO BADALAMENTI (0000-0002-2395-454X)

Organizations

National Research Council Institute for the Study of Anthropic Impacts, University of Gothenburg – Kristineberg Marine Research Station, University of Edinburgh

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Wind or Current: Determining the key driver in seagrass floating fruit dispersal to optimize seed collection for aquaculture/restoration purposes](#)

Description:

This project aims to experimentally quantify the movement ecology of *Posidonia oceanica* fruits under controlled conditions, using a current flume to simulate realistic combinations of currents and wind observed at sea. We aim to measure fruit speeds under 10 current and 8 wind intensities and 2 wind directions to provide useful data to model dispersal distances and trajectories of fruits at sea. In addition, improved identification of beachcast sites could facilitate seed collection efforts, making seed-based restoration techniques more practical and scalable. This approach would support the production of seedlings for transplantation, facilitating both aquaculture applications and large-scale *Posidonia oceanica* restoration initiatives.

All raw and processed data generated during this project, along with descriptive metadata and relevant scripts, will be deposited in the open-access repository Zenodo. The data will be made publicly available under a CC-BY 4.0 license after publication of the associated peer-reviewed article. An embargo may apply until formal publication to ensure proper referencing and citation

Researchers:

[Eduardo Infantes \(0000-0002-9724-9237\)](#)

[Arturo Zenone \(0000-0001-5540-7148\)](#)

[Trace Laskey \(0009-0001-4299-4846\)](#)

[FABIO BADALAMENTI \(0000-0002-2395-454X\)](#)

Organizations:

[National Research Council Institute for the Study of Anthropic Impacts](#)

[University of Gothenburg – Kristineberg Marine Research Station](#)

[University of Edinburgh](#)

Contact: [Badalamenti Fabio \(fabio.badalamenti@cnr.it\)](mailto:fabio.badalamenti@cnr.it)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [AQUASERV](#)

Data Management Plan | [Wind or Current: Determining the key driver in seagrass floating fruit dispersal to optimize seed collection for aquaculture/restoration purposes](#)

LICENSE:Zenodo DOI: - 13/07/2025

Grants: [AQUASERV – RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE SERVICES FOR SUSTAINABLE AQUACULTURE, FISHERIES AND THE BLUE ECONOMY \(corda_____he::101131121\)](#)

Project: [AQUASERV – Posidonia oceanica fruit dispersal at Kristineberg](#)

3. License

License: [Zenodo](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

[Horizon Europe - Ethics](#)

This project aims to experimentally quantify the movement ecology of *Posidonia oceanica* fruits under controlled conditions, using a current flume to simulate realistic combinations of currents and wind observed at sea. We aim to measure fruit speeds under 10 current and 8 wind intensities and 2 wind directions to provide useful data to model dispersal distances and trajectories of fruits at sea. In addition, improved identification of beach-cast sites could facilitate seed collection efforts, making seed-based restoration techniques more practical and scalable. This approach supports the production of seedlings for transplantation, benefiting both aquaculture applications and large-scale *Posidonia oceanica* restoration initiatives.

Template: [Horizon Europe - Ethics](#)

Type: [Ethics](#)

1 Ethics

1.1 Ethics

1.1.1 Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Data Management Plan | Wind or Current: Determining the key driver in seagrass floating fruit dispersal to optimize seed collection for aquaculture/restoration purposes

LICENSE: [Zenodo](#) DOI: - 13/07/2025

No

No ethics or legal issues are foreseen that would prevent data sharing. An embargo period may apply purely for publication timing, not for ethical/legal reason

1.1.2 Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

No

Powered by

